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INTERAKCJA SZKOLNICTWA WYŻSZEGO I RYNKU PRACY: DOŚWIADCZENIE I PERSPEKTYWY

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Streszczenie. W artykule przeanalizowano współczesne tendencje współdziałania szkolnictwa wyższego i rynku pracy, określono mechanizmy funkcjonowania w oświatowej branży.

Opisano główne kierunki realizacji modelu współdziałania Tarnopolskiego Narodowego Uniwersytetu Pedagogicznego i rynku pracy: pomoc w zatrudnieniu studentów i absolwentów uniwersytetu, stworzenie odpowiednich warunków działania oraz efektywnego rozwoju młodzieżowej przedsiębiorczości; pomoc w tymczasowym zatrudnieniu studentów w czasie wolnym od zajęć; ustalenie socjalnego partnerstwa z przedsiębiorstwami, instytucjami, organizacjami (pracodawcami) itp.

Udowodniono, że najbardziej aktualnym wskaźnikiem współpracy między uczelnią a rynkiem pracy jest zatrudnienie absolwentów, więc rozwikłanie tego problemu zależy od wielu czynników, takich jak: jakość przygotowania fachowców na uczelniach wyższych; udoskonalenie programów przygotowania, które uwzględniają perspektywy rozwoju branży; struktura i zakres przygotowania specjalistów w regionie, posiadających wykształcenie wyższe, ich zgodność z potrzebami rynku pracy; kształtowanie indywidualnych cech studentów niezbędnych na rynku pracy; adaptacja młodych fachowców do warunków pracy, rozwój programów społecznych oraz wsparcie w miejscu pracy; stworzenie warunków do samorealizacji młodzieży.

Szczególną uwagę zwrócono na kluczowe czynniki mające wpływ na przygotowanie fachowców posiadających zdolność konkurencyjną oraz popierają współdziałanie szkolnictwa wyższego a rynku pracy.

Przytoczono doświadczenie współpracy między Tarnopolskim Narodowym Uniwersytetem Pedagogicznym a pracodawcami. W TNUP opracowano skuteczny mechanizm otrzymania informacji zwrotnej udzielanej przez rynek pracy. W szczególności, ciągle podtrzymują się relacje wzajemnie korzystne z wewnętrznymi i międzynarodowymi pracodawcami, przeprowadza się konsultacje w celu dostosowania programów edukacyjnych, dążeniem których jest wykształcenie fachowców wysokiej klasy, którzy potrafią wytrzymać konkurencję na rynku pracy.

Udowodniono, że rozwój nowych podejść efektywnego współdziałania szkolnictwa wyższego i rynku pracy we współczesnych warunkach zapewnia skuteczne funkcjonowanie systemu szkolnictwa wyższego.

Słowa kluczowe: współdziałanie, rynek pracy, szkolnictwo wyższe, przygotowanie, fachowiec, konkurencja.

INTERACTION BETWEEN HIGHER EDUCATION AND THE LABOUR MARKET: EXPERIENCE AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract. The article analyses the current trends of interaction between higher education and the labour market, identifies the mechanisms of its functioning in the field of education.

The main directions of realization of the model of interaction of Ternopil National Pedagogical University and the labour market are revealed. They are assistance in employment of students and graduates of higher education institution, creation of appropriate conditions for functioning and effective development of youth entrepreneurship; promotion of temporary employment of students in their free time; establishment of social partnership with enterprises, institutions and organizations (employers), etc.

It is proved that the most relevant indicator of the interaction between higher education institutions (HEIs) and the labour market is the employment of graduates. It depends on many factors, such as: the quality of training in higher education institutions; improvement of training programs that take into account the prospects of the industry; structure and programmes of training specialists of higher education in the region, the compliance of the programmes with the needs of the labour market; training students' personal qualities demanded by the labour market; adaptation of young professionals to working conditions, development of mentoring, social programs to support them in the workplace; creating conditions for self-realization of youth.

The factors that influence the training of a competitive specialist and contribute to the intensification of the interaction of the labour market and higher education are identified.

The experience of interaction of Ternopil National Pedagogical University with employers is shared. TNPU has developed a clear mechanism for receiving feedback from the labour market about its graduates. In particular, relations with domestic and international employers are constantly maintained, consultations are held in order to timely review educational programs, to ensure the quality of training in conditions of fierce competition in the labour market.

It is proved that the development of new approaches to the effective interaction of higher education and the labour market in modern conditions is the key to successful functioning of the higher education system.

Key words: interaction, labour market, higher education, training, specialist, competition.

ВЗАЄМОДІЯ ВИЩОЇ ОСВІТИ І РИНКУ ПРАЦІ: ДОСВІД ТА ПЕРСПЕКТИВИ

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Анотація. У статті проаналізовано сучасні тенденції взаємодії вищої освіти та ринку праці, визначено механізми її функціонування в освітній галузі. Розкрито основні напрями реалізації моделі взаємодії Тернопільського національного педагогічного університету і ринку праці: сприяння працевлаштуванню студентів та випускників закладу вищої освіти, створення відповідних умов функціонування та ефективного розвитку молодіжного підприємництва; сприяння тимчасовому працевлаштуванню студентів у вільний від навчання час; встановлення соціального партнерства з підприємствами, установами та організаціями (роботодавцями) тощо.

Доведено, що найбільш актуальним показником взаємодії ЗВО і ринку праці є працевлаштування випускників, а розв'язання цієї проблеми залежить від багатьох чинників, таких як: якість підготовки фахівців у закладах вищої освіти; вдосконалення програм підготовки, що враховують перспективи розвитку галузі; структура та обсяг підготовки фахівців з вищою освітою в регіоні, їх відповідність потребам ринку праці; виховання у студентів затребуваних ринком праці особистісних якостей; адаптація молодих фахівців до умов праці, розвиток наставництва, соціальних програм їх підтримки на робочому місці; створення умов для самореалізації молоді.

Виокремлено чинники, які впливають на підготовку конкурентноспроможного фахівця та сприяють активізації взаємодії ринку праці та вищої освіти. Наведено досвід взаємодії Тернопільського національного педагогічного університету з роботодавцями. В ТНПУ розроблено чіткий механізм отримання зворотного зв'язку від ринку праці про його випускників. Зокрема, постійно підтримуються відносини з внутрішніми і міжнародними роботодавцями, проводяться консультації з метою своєчасного перегляду освітніх програм, для забезпечення якості підготовки в умовах жорсткої конкуренції на ринку праці.

Доведено, що розвиток нових підходів ефективної взаємодії вищої освіти і ринку праці в сучасних умовах є запорукою успішного функціонування системи вищої освіти.

Ключові слова: взаємодія, ринок праці, вища освіта, підготовка, фахівець, конкуренція.

Innovative processes in modern economy directly affect the realm of education that is an integral part of public life. Today, the higher education institution is a phenomenon of both markets – the educational and labour. The nature of the interaction of these entities is determined by a set of economic, social and institutional relations in the process of quality training of future professionals.

Modernization of the education system is based on the awareness of the trends in foreign and domestic development, on the scientific analysis of the needs of society and the individual, the accurate choice and sequence of actions in establishing state educational policy. The problems faced by graduates of higher education institutions (*hereinafter HEIs*) have made them think about the need for close collaboration between

universities and employers, adaptation of educational programs to labour market requirements. The National Strategy for Education Development in Ukraine for 2012-2021 states that the structure and content of vocational, higher and postgraduate education lack orientation towards the needs of the labour market and current economic challenges, there is a failure of an effective system of employment of freelance graduates, their professional support (*Shaulska, Yakymova 2017, 143*). The matter of urgency of the outlined problem is raised due to the fact that higher education lags significantly behind the processes taking place in society and does not meet the demands of the labour market. There is a gap in the relationship between the free economic zone and institutions and enterprises. Insufficient monitoring of the dynamics of the labour market leads to a decrease in the quality of professional training of freelance graduates. There are also inconsistencies between higher education performance and labour market expectations that hinder the development of their effective partnership. (*Law of Ukraine 2018*).

With this in mind, the higher education system should work in accordance with the labour market. It has to promote the development of in-demand professional competencies, such as the ability to quickly adapt and apply knowledge in non-standard situations, the desire for professional growth and self-improvement. With increasing competition from higher education institutions, there is a need to find effective mechanisms that would ensure competitiveness and achieve the expected results in the long run (*Shtepa 2015, 67*).

The problem of formation, development and regulation of labour and education markets is actualized in the researches of Ukrainian scientists, such as O. Hrishnova, N. Fedak, V. Oliynyk, V. Andrushchenko, I. Vasylenko, L. Drobysch and I. Kyrychenko. Significant contributions to the theory and methodology of regulation of labour and education markets were made by such scholars as S. Bandur, S. Hrynkevych, I. Hnibidenko, I. Bezsonova, A. Kolot, L. Lisogor, I. Petrova, V. Onikienko, G. Pilipenko, L. Shaulska and others. L. Ilyich, A. Zabolotny, I. Kimova, O. Osinkina, N. Leshchenko are studying international experience and Ukrainian practice in establishing partnerships between business and the state in the realm of education. At the same time, the problem of interaction of labour and education markets, subject-object relationships, their institutional functioning are still lacking in an applied aspect, which determines the relevance of the research issue.

The objective of the article is to analyse current trends in the interaction of higher education and the labour market, to determine the mechanism of their functioning in higher education, to reveal the main directions of implementation of the model of interaction between higher education and the labour market.

The system of higher education and the requirements for its content are evolving along with the development of Ukrainian society. The market economy puts forward new demands to freelance graduates and the quality of their professional training is one of the most important strategic tasks. The success of an educational institution depends on the competitiveness and demand of its graduates in the labour market, the compliance of educational programs with the requirements of employers (*National Qualifications Framework 2019*). Modern universities create models of specialists in two areas: first, models that involve the greatest focus on state standards and requirements of regional structures – universities and employers; second, models focused on the needs of specific

customers, as well as on the training of specialists for the most flexible and dynamic areas (financial sphere, communication technologies, etc.).

To improve the quality of higher education in modern conditions and prepare students for professional life outside the free economic zone, it is necessary to actively implement a more applied approach to education. Building and expanding partnerships between academia and the public and private sectors is an integral part of this process. The interaction between higher education institutions and the labour market includes the following aspects:

- formation of a joint strategy of establishments, organizations and HEIs;
- joint development and implementation of popular programs and involvement of students into practical activities;
- active participation of specialists-practitioners in the educational process of HEIs;
- ensuring the autonomy and financial independence of educational institutions;
- issuing the state order as to the number of experts needed by the labour market;
- encouraging employers to joint research cooperation with the HEIs in priority areas.

The mechanism of interaction between the labour market and education is quite natural and is based on social partnership of all stakeholders. The interaction has many ways and methods that, if used effectively, can help solve the problem of mismatch of qualifications with labour market needs, achieve a balance between employment security and labour market flexibility. The most relevant indicator of this interaction is the employment of graduates, and the solution to this problem depends on many factors, in particular:

- the quality of training in higher education institutions;
- development of training programs that take into account the prospects of the industry;
- structure and programme of graduates' training in the region, their compliance with the needs of the labour market;
- education of students' personal qualities required in the labour market;
- adaptation of young professionals to working conditions, development of mentoring, social programs to support them in the workplace;
- creating conditions for self-realization of the youth.

Taking into consideration the specific interests and relationships of higher education institutions with employers, it is worth mentioning not only the systematic interaction, but the direct involvement in the educational process, which affects the quality of training. Solving the outlined problems will help to improve the quality of training of graduates of higher education institutions in accordance with the requirements of employers, the formation of a positive image of higher education institutions among applicantsx (*Boyko 2015, 266*).

In the context of reforming the education sector, implementing the Concept of the New Ukrainian School, Ternopil National Pedagogical University (hereinafter TNPU) is looking for ways of effective, comprehensive cooperation between the university and the employer, which contributes to quality training and demand in the labour market. To make this happen, the university has developed an institutional model of internal quality assurance of education which is one of the necessary organizational conditions for successful operation of higher education. This institutional model is characterized by

flexibility, mobility, self-realization and leadership potential of all participants in the educational process. The development and implementation of the model contribute to the active interaction of the administration, faculty, heads of departments, teachers, external and internal stakeholders, i.e. customers and consumers of educational services.

There are clear procedures of how it works in TNPU. The council of external stakeholders controls and in the process of improving the quality of educational services internal stakeholders actively interact. The Centre for Educational Quality Assurance systematically conducts surveys of teachers and school principals on the quality of training of future specialists. Recently an online survey of university stakeholders has been developed and implemented. The monitoring results are discussed at a meeting of the Academic Council, the Commission for Internal Quality Assurance of Education, faculty councils, etc.

In order to increase the competitiveness of graduates, Ternopil National Pedagogical University (TNPU) has developed a clear strategy for the interaction of the university with the labour market. These are some of the activities:

1. TNPU carries out constant analysis of demand in the labour market of experts trained by the university.

2. Cooperation with the state employment service, enterprises, institutions and organizations, regardless of ownership, which may be potential employers for graduates and students has been established.

3. Ensuring coordination of actions with central and local executive bodies, employment services, enterprises, institutions and organizations (employers) on the optimal coordination of real needs of the labour market and educational services.

4. Informing graduates and students of the university about vacancies in institutions and organizations that correspond to their professional training (specialty).

5. Monitoring the employment of graduates at the place of their residence together with the state employment service.

The model of partnership between TNPU and the labour market includes the following areas:

- assistance in employment of students and graduates of higher education institutions, their adaptation to the dynamics of demand of specialists in the labour market;

- involvement of student youth in entrepreneurial activity, creation of appropriate conditions for the functioning and effective development of youth entrepreneurship;

- promotion of temporary employment of students in their free time;

- establishing social partnership with enterprises, institutions and organizations (employers);

- introduction of feedback system between enterprises, institutions and organizations (employers) and HEIs to obtain an objective assessment of the quality of professional training;

- TNPU takes part in the process of preparing and implementing regional employment programs;

- study, dissemination of the best domestic and international experience in vocational training of young people and their employment;

- conducting explanatory work among students and graduates on legislative and regulatory acts in the framework of state regulation of employment and labour relations.

To improve the interaction of the university with employers, TNPU has developed a clear mechanism for receiving feedback from the labour market on the employment of graduates. In particular, relations are constantly maintained by employers, consultations are held in order to timely adjust educational programs to ensure the proper quality of education in conditions of fierce competition in the labour market and economic situation. This approach to the effective interaction of higher education and the labour market in modern conditions is the key to successful functioning of the education sector. The development of an interaction system between the HEIs and the labour market will be beneficial for all the parties. Employers cut their expenses on search and staff training, as well as increase productivity in a particular firm. Students open up possibilities of successful employment and career advancement after graduation. HEIs build up their reputation and receive a high rating in the labour market and educational services.

Therefore, to improve the quality of higher education in modern conditions, the training of a competitive specialist must take into account the factors that contribute to the interaction of the labour market and higher education:

- constant adaptation of the content and forms of education to the transformation of labour markets in the information society, rapid changes in traditional social and professional roles;
- providing scientific and pedagogical workers with the necessary technological and information resources;
- the use of modern information and communication technologies to individualize the educational process, predicting and taking into account the expectations of different students;
- active involvement of employers in reviewing and improving educational programs;
- studying best practices and testing forms and technologies of dual education;
- interaction of teaching staff with practitioners in the educational process of the HEIs;
- labour market monitoring and employment promotion system for graduates of higher education institutions;
- development of dual education, i.e. employment of graduates in a way of a tripartite agreement “graduate – institution of higher education – employer”

Therefore, in the process of interaction with the labour market, HEIs should create appropriate mechanisms to improve the quality and efficiency of education, as well as meet the needs of the recipient of educational services. They should assess the real needs and problems of students, provide information and assist them in employment. Successful graduates who have achieved the best results need to develop “career strategies” together with interested representatives of the labour market. The positive impact of the integration of educational and production processes on the quality of training confirms the need to develop comprehensive cooperation between higher education institutions and real employers. Such cooperation is mutually beneficial for all its participants, and what is more important, for future professionals.

In order to prevent oversaturation of the labour market by university graduates in certain specialties, it is necessary to monitor the balance of both markets. The higher educational institutions have to interact with potential employers in order to identify current needs and make appropriate adjustments to training programs.

According to the study, the mechanism of interaction between labour markets and education is quite natural and is based on social partnership of all stakeholders. It contains a large number of ways and methods that, if used effectively, can help solve the problem of mismatch of qualifications with the needs of the labour market, achieving a balance between employment and income security and labour market flexibility. Long-term tasks are manifested in the organization of advanced development and renewal of the training process (retraining), training in accordance with long-term plans of social and economic development with the gradual achievement of greater flexibility of these market systems.

Prospective research in this direction will be aimed at improving the socio-economic mechanism of interaction between labour markets and education, substantiation of educational structure, methodological, institutional and resource provision.

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